

Canagliflozin lowers blood sugar, but does it also lower cardiovascular risk? Maybe not.

For the last 25 years, it has been widely accepted that diabetes mellitus is associated with a twofold or greater risk of clinical atherosclerotic disease. Long-standing elevated blood sugar levels, as measured by the hemoglobin A1c level, be independent of major cardiovascular risk factors, including age, body mass index, systolic blood pressure, serum cholesterol, cigarette smoking, or history of cardiovascular disease.

Citation: Heston TF, Olson AH, Randall NR. Canagliflozin lowers blood sugar, but does it also lower cardiovascular risk? Maybe not. *Ann Transl Med* 2017;5(23):473. doi:

[10.21037/atm.2017.09.28](https://doi.org/10.21037/atm.2017.09.28)